

A Women in Crop Science Conversation with ... Beatrice Ifie

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Background

Beatrice Elohor Ifie, born in Nigeria, obtained her first degree in Botany at the University of Ibadan, Nigeria. Because of her interest in helping farmers through crop improvement, she proceeded to study Agriculture and obtained a Master's degree in Plant Breeding at the Department of Agronomy from the same university. After her master's she achieved her Doctoral degree in Plant Breeding at the West Africa Centre for Crop Improvement (WACCI), University of Ghana (UG).

Currently she is leading the Miscanthus Breeding Programme at the Institute of Biological, Environmental and Rural Sciences (IBERS) at the Aberystwyth University in the UK. Before joining IBERS, she was a Senior Lecturer at the University of Ghana and the Leader of the Maize Breeding Programme at WACCI.

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Can you briefly describe what you do?

My research is on improving crop plants for high yield and resilience. I have worked on several food crops, but mostly focused on maize until recently when my interest shifted to the energy crop, Miscanthus. I currently lead the Miscanthus Breeding Programme at the Institute of Biological, Environmental and Rural Sciences (IBERS), Aberystwyth University. Before joining IBERS, I was a Senior Lecturer at the University of Ghana (UG) and Leader of the Maize Breeding Programme at the West Africa Centre for Crop Improvement (WACCI) at the University of Ghana.

Why did you get into research and especially Crop Science?

I would say it is by fate as my initial intent was to study medicine, but I ended up studying Crop Science. As a young undergraduate Plant Science student, the career path was not clear to me, not until I had the opportunity to work as an intern at the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA). The exposure I got from that internship changed it all for me. The experience stimulated my fascination for research in plant breeding. I saw the opportunities available in the field to contribute to science for impact and development, I went for it and there has been no looking back.

Lab or field? Field

Conference or stakeholder meeting? Both, it really depends on the relevance of the theme of the meeting.

Literature review or project report? Literature review

Conventional or molecular methods? Both methods are complementary!

Hybrid, inbred or vegetative? It depends on the crop.

Qualitative or quantitative research? It depends on the traits of interest.

GenStat or R? R

Favourite crop & why? I do not have a favourite crop. Each crop has its own uniqueness.

What do you love the most about your job?

The new experience it offers to contribute to science for impact and development. I enjoy making crosses, creating useful variation, and selecting plants with desirable characteristics.

Any major hurdles?

Limited grant opportunities for plant breeding.

Who has influenced you the most and why?

Several people have influenced me in so many ways. To mention a few, I would say my dad, who started the conversation of a PhD before I even thought of it. Then, Prof. Eric Yirenkyi Danquah, the Director of WACCI, a mentor and a visionary leader who put within me the drive for excellence and opportunities to grow professionally.

Most important publication or the publication of which you are most proud?

The publication from my PhD, which has received the most citations:

Ifie, B. E., Badu-Apraku, B., Gracen, V., & Danquah, E. Y. (2015). [Genetic Analysis of Grain Yield of IITA and CIMMYT Early-Maturing Maize Inbreds under Striga-Infested and Low-Soil-Nitrogen Environments](#). *Crop Science*, 55(2), 610-623.

What is your favourite aspect of your research?

Receiving positive feedback from farmers and other stakeholders on potential of our crop varieties and its socioeconomic and environmental impact.

Beach or mountain? Beach

Tea or coffee? I am making some effort to drink tea and coffee. Both are on the same scale for me.

Appetizer or dessert? Dessert. I always reserve space for dessert!

Instagram or Twitter? Twitter

Fame or fortune? Both

Many thanks to Beatrice for participating in the Women in Crop Science conversations series and we look forward to following your career as it progresses.